

**AESTHETIC PRINCIPLES OF DISTINGUISHING LAUGHTER
THROUGH PARALINGUISTIC AND MAKORONISMS IN THE WORKS
OF O'TKIR HASHIMOV**

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Abstract: In this article, the aesthetic principles of distinguishing laughter through paralinguistic and makoronisms in the works of O'tkir Hashimov are scientifically and theoretically analyzed based on artistic texts.

Key words: Irony, laughter, macaroonism, occasionalism, phonetic and mimic paralinguistics, homophone, homograph, imitation, borrowed word, florionym, etc.

Introduction: The musical tone and sincerity of the works of the People's Writer of Uzbekistan O'tkir Hashimov fascinates every reader. The reason for this is the attractiveness and folkliness of literary works. In the comic stories of the writer, this charm and sincerity are the priority.

Review of literature: In the conditions of the established regime, O'tkir Hashimov gained attention among the people with his honest words. The writer always tried to say the right thing in his works. That is why the author's stories, plays, and novels are among the favorite works of our people. Another characteristic of O'tkir Hashimov is that the writer never told a lie, he did not sell his conscience by playing to the drum of authoritarian ideology and politics, he did not enter the path of compromise. He did not give in to passing trends, but was interested in the art of words as an expression of his eternal problem - the puzzle of personality, the feeling of social justice. We want to talk about various expressions of irony and laughter in the works of O'tkir Hashimov. As evidence of our opinion, we refer to some stories of the writer:

"In the morning, when I was waiting to hear my horse "dragon", a voice came to my ears saying: "Stay still, my friend, your tea will get cold..." he is smiling above me. "Happy Birthday to you! May God bless your life!" - he kissed my face, this face. While kissing, he was surprised by the "muttar" smell that came from my mouth and did not notice it. Look at this, we almost forgot our birthday..."¹There is a phenomenon of paralinguistics in Uzbek linguistics. Paralinguistics is derived from

¹Hoshimov.O'. So'qqabosh bevagina. "Ajdar"ning tavbasi.Toshkent 2022. Nurli Dunyo nashriyoti. 9-bet.

the Latin word meaning "approach with language". The pineapple of increasing the effectiveness of works of art and giving aesthetic pleasure to the reader through paralinguistic phenomena is reflected in this excerpt - "smiling-i-i-ib".

-Hey, megajin! - he said in a low but threatening tone. - You go to the bank at ten o'clock in the morning! If you don't go and transfer eighteen million to my account, I'll pull your hair out! Transfer the money and send the order number to my e-mail! A woman has only one thing to say, do you understand?²

In Uzbek linguistics, there is a phenomenon of creating laughter by using or distorting international words received from abroad. This phenomenon is called makoronisms. In the artistic language we have taken: words like "Lichno", "ravno", "porucheniye" are considered makoronisms. Here, international expressions are usually used.

You say that you will eat madarsomsa, but we say no, my dear! - he said with a womanly determination. - Just remember what to put in it! Tomorrow I will go to Oloy base with "telexes" and show everything, dear! Momintoy ran away.

"I'm going to the market," he said with a smile. - You will enter the green square. A garden of green onions, a garden of mint in a bag...³

In the mentioned artistic mant, the macaronomy of "salapan (cellophane)" was distorted by pronouncing it according to the dialect, and it served to make the reader laugh in the artistic work.

In addition, in Uzbek literature, faunisms (by quoting animals), florionyms (by simulating plant names with human characteristics) and parenthetical (by side-by-side use of internal and external speech), paradoxical (existing event to event by giving the opposite definition), presuppositional (by expressing the negative characteristics of the image that the author is admitting), occasional (by means of words that appear by chance in the speech but are not found in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language) .

You say that you will eat madarsomsa, but we say no, my dear! - he said with a womanly determination. - Just remember what to put in it! Tomorrow I will go to Oloy base with "telexes" and show everything, dear! Momintoy ran away.

² Hoshimov.O'. "Ajdar"ning tavbasi.Mo'mintoy. Toshkent 2023. Nurli Dunyo nashriyoti. 12-bet.

³ Hoshimov.O'. "Ajdar"ning tavbasi.Mo'mintoy. Toshkent 2023. Nurli Dunyo nashriyoti. 11-bet.

"I'm going to the market," he said with a smile. - You will enter the green square. A garden of green onions, a garden of mint in a bag...⁴

In this literary text: "madorsomsa" is an occasional word.

May your hands break the cup after putting salt in the tea and saying, "Why isn't your sugar sweet?" Let the sniper's bullet hit your eyes that sparkle like pearls! May the tongues of those who drank pasta soup and scolded my mother saying "why is your lagma dough like a boy" be minced in an electric mixer! May your nose, which is wrinkled like an eggplant left in the sun, fall off! Kasim is like a curd maker, let him rot in the kitchen! It's rotten! Does not rot. If someone puts a reed on the gourd and lights a match, it will burn as an "eternal flame" for forty years! A member of the body has turned into alcohol!⁵

In this artistic text: "your nose as wrinkled as an eggplant" are flaronyms. Words like "sniper's bullet", "elektricheskiy myasorubka", "eternal flame" are examples of makoronisms.

Conclusion: Otkir Hashimov's stories and short stories are read like poems and epics, they sound like a charming melody played in single words, his novels are reminiscent of a multi-voiced symphony, even when reading his works and journalistic articles, one can feel the treasure of the human heart, emotions. their various glosses are embodied, from simple everyday experiences to huge social observations, intense spiritual dramas, tragedies, and nightmares, they never leave the feeling of sophistication, even in extremely dense scenes, there is a strange sincerity, humor and light. the melody echoes. This is one of the secrets of the charm of Otkir Hashimov's prose.

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⁴ Hoshimov.O'. "Ajdar"ning tavbasi.Mo'mintoy. Toshkent 2023. Nurli Dunyo nashriyoti. 11-bet.

⁵ Hoshimov.O'. So'qqabosh bevagina. "Ajdar"ning tavbasi.Toshkent 2022. Nurli Dunyo nashriyoti. 9-bet.

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